

Numerical modeling and experimental realization of wide bandgap ZnTe-based solar cells for semi-transparent PV application

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Abstract — We report on the modeling of semi-transparent ZnTe-based photovoltaic devices. We propose innovative strategies to markedly improve the performances, so far mostly hindered by a poor band alignment at the p-n interface. Alternative buffer materials are considered, and we investigate on the surface selenization of the ZnTE films as well as the feasibility of a purely ZnTe homojunction. Using a realistic set of state-of-the-art parameters, a semi-transparent solar cell with a potential efficiency exceeding 7.5% is demonstrated possible.

Index Terms — numerical modeling building integrated photovoltaics, Zinc Telluride, semi-transparent, thin film.

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic energy has now reached a state of maturity with several single junction technologies largely exceeding the 20% mark and available at a very competitive cost [1]. Moving forward, we identify two directions which can further help the field evolving toward larger scale deployment. Firstly, as single junction efficiencies are closing the gap with the Shockley-Queisser (SQ) limit, additional gains will mostly be obtained using the disruptive approaches labelled as third generation photovoltaics, among which tandem solar cells are the only current devices demonstrating performances above the SQ limit. However, this technology remains costly and mostly focuses on using III-V single crystal materials and developing low cost alternative covering a wide array of bandgaps is a necessity in that context. Secondly, building integration and social acceptance of photovoltaics are key challenges to tackle and proposing efficient semi-transparent devices addresses a currently untapped potential for the PV technology and its integration in an urban environment.

ZnTe holds several assets to address both of these pathways, being a naturally p-doped wide bandgap (2.3eV) compound [2], and being already used as back electron reflector in the highly efficient CdTe technology [3]. It also addresses a range in the solar spectrum where few inorganic PV materials exist as most semi-transparent cells reported so far use less stable organic molecules [4]. The use of ZnTe as a PV absorber has been surprisingly seldom reported from its first introduction by H.W. Schock and F. Pfisterer in the early 80s [5]. In those studies, the PV performances always remained below 2%, largely below 1% even, far from living up to this material's potential (about 13% in the SQ limit). Those studies all identified the p-n

junction conduction band cliff-like misalignment as the main factor hindering the solar cell's voltage and hence the efficiency

$$(\chi_{\text{ZnTe}} = 3.6\text{eV}).$$

Based on these studies and using unidimensional numerical modeling (SCAPS 3.3), we propose in this work three strategies addressing this roadblock, each focusing on the p-n interface and with the possibility to be to some extent combined, though we will consider them separately here to keep the model as close as possible to what can realistically be achieved. We first investigate on different n-doped partners (buffer layers) to p-ZnTe, based on commonly used buffer layers in the CIGSSe/CdTe technology. Owing to its low electron affinity $\chi_{\text{ZnS}} = 3.9\text{eV}$, ZnS is found to yield a significantly lesser band offset and thus higher efficiency than its counterparts previously used to fabricate ZnTe solar cells, and is thus a prime candidate to fabricate semi-transparent devices with efficiencies exceeding 5%.

The front alloying of ZnTe absorbers with Se is also investigated. This approach holds two important characteristics helping to increase the efficiency, as it simultaneously lowers the valence band and to a lesser extent the conduction band near the p-n interface. This helps repelling holes from the junction (similarly to what is done with the front sulfurization of CIGSe absorbers), while allowing for a better matching of χ between the p-absorber and the n-partner layer. The front selenization of ZnTe absorber is thus found to markedly improve performances with an optimum thickness at or below the space charge region value.

Finally, the possibility of n-doping ZnTe layers (using Al or Cl) is considered as a pathway to realize ZnTe homojunction [6], [7], thus fully alleviating the issues related to the n-partner layer. We specifically investigate on the position of the homojunction through the absorber, specifically identifying the space charge region as the key area where the efficiency can be markedly improved. An optimum position of the p-n interface is determined fully unlocking the voltage of the device.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ZnTe solar cells are modeled using SCAPS 3.3. The material parameters for each layer are taken from state of the art values reported in the literature, as well as from in-house characterizations. The modeled structure is as follows: Metal/1 m-ZnTe/n-Buffer/ITO metal, and the metal/semiconductor interfaces are considered perfectly ohmic; a reasonable assumption considering that ZnTe is being used as back contact in CdTe solar cells.

As pointed out in the introduction, the low electron affinity

Figure 1 Modeled current-voltage curves of ZnTe solar cells with different n-doped partner materials.

of ZnTe is challenging for the formation of a p-n interface with no voltage limitation from the conduction band mismatch. As reported in reference [5], interfacing ZnTe with CdS leads to a voltage equivalent to that of a Cu₂S solar cell, with the voltage losses at the interface corresponding exactly to $\chi_{EC} = 0.9\text{eV}$.

As a first strategy, we investigate on the potential of In₂S₃ and ZnS compared with CdS, as shown in figure 1. Although not with a perfect band matching on ZnTe with a cliff-like misalignment of 0.3eV, using ZnS as a buffer layer leads to a significant improvement of the voltage from 0.98V to 1.24V while the other PV parameters remain roughly unchanged, and an efficiency of 6.0% is then achievable. In₂S₃, with its much higher electron affinity, yields the lowest performance though it is worth mentioning that while not considered in the Anderson model [8], interfacial layers and Fermi level pinning often help to alleviate the voltage limitation and so, this option should not be fully discarded in future experiments.

Further enhancement of the PV performances is possible when tuning the interface similarly to what is done when sulfurizing CIGSSe absorbers [9], though using Se as substitution for Te. A ZnS buffer layer is considered in this model. The introduction of thin Zn(Te,Se) layer with a linearly graded Se/Te composition at the p-n interface is modeled by simultaneously varying the selenization depth from 0 to 500nm

and the Se/Te composition from 0 to 0.5, leading to the surface plots presented in figure 2 (ZnS being in this case the n-doped buffer layer).

Figure 2 Surface plots of the photovoltaic parameters as a function of the Se/Te front composition and the selenization depth.

The front Se/(Se+Te) ratio appears as driving the Voc increase with a relatively limited influence of the selenization depth. We also notice that the cell's current is preserved from the increase Se/(Se+Te) composition, as long as the thickness of the selenized layer is below 200nm (roughly equivalent to the space charge region width), and remains above 6mA.cm⁻². For deeper selenized layer however, a sharp drop is observed as the Zn(Se,Te) layer's contribution to the photovoltaic effect starts to overcome that of the ZnTe. Such observation echoes a similar phenomenon previously shown on CIGSSe [10]. While the FF remains at a high value for high Se/(Se+Te) front

composition and limited selenized thicknesses, a sharp decline is observed when the selenization depth is increased. As the front material's bandgap increases beyond the depth of the space charge region, the alignment of the holes' Fermi level with that of the metallic back contact pushes the conduction band upward while the valence band remains flat between the ZnTe/Zn(Te,Se) films, resulting in the formation of a barrier near the interface hindering the electronic transport, and thus affecting the FF of the device. A sweet spot with efficiencies above 7.5% is observed for a Se/Te front composition of 0.3~0.5 and a selenization depth of 30nm~200nm, that is below the space charge region width as previously mentioned, echoing again what is observed in CIGSSe. This remarkable increase of the efficiency as compared to pure ZnTe is ascribed to the lowering of the valence band, hence acting as "front surface field" for the hole, driving them away from the space charge region and thus markedly reducing the interface recombinations, which was observed in the results of our model (not shown here).

Finally, n-doping of ZnTe has been reported by migration of Al or Cl atoms, which opens the possibility of realizing p-ZnTe/n-ZnTe [7]. We modeled such structure by replacing the n-doped partner material by n-doped ZnTe, using material parameters from literature [11], while keeping the front ITO unchanged. On Figure 3, the position of the p-n junction is varied throughout the thickness of the absorber, showing that a substantial efficiency improvement is potentially achievable in an homojunction configuration.

Figure 3 Photovoltaic parameters as a function of the junction depth.

Specifically, we notice that the short circuit current remains stable for junction depth roughly similar to that of the space charge region (about 200nm). For deeper junctions however, carriers absorbed in the n-side of the junction are not efficiently collected owing to the low hole mobility in n-doped ZnTe. On the other hand, a balanced homojunction increases as expected the voltage of the cell, maximizing the difference between electrons and holes' extraction energy. An efficiency exceeding 7% is found possible, for a 100nm-deep homojunction, which is exactly the middle of the space charge region on both sides.

III. CONCLUSION

Within the landscape of inorganic wide bandgap materials, ZnTe is an interesting yet overlooked materials, until now held back from reaching its potential by several issues which we believe have been identified in this study. As the band matching at the p-n interface hinders the voltage of the solar cell, three strategies are proposed to overcome this problem, and their potential is evaluated using a simple unidimensional numerical modeling approach. As expected, ZnS shows a significant

improvement over the previously tested CdS n-buffer layer, with a much better conduction band alignment with ZnTe. The introduction of a thin selenized layer at the surface of the ZnTe absorber shows great promises for further enhancing the voltage without degrading the current, by creating a hole front surface field limiting the interface recombinations similarly to the sulfurization of CIGSe films. ZnTe homojunctions are also considered as viable alternative to standard n-buffer layers.

Preliminary ongoing experiments demonstrate the feasibility of solar-grade quality ZnTe using an industry compatible deposition process in sputtering and Te-atmosphere thermal annealing. Complete solar cell devices are being processed at the time of this proceeding, and the results will be presented at a later date.

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